

Supplementary information:

Revealing nanoscale plasticity of metallic nanosponges with correlative and scale-bridging 3D microscopy and modelling

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SI Figure 1: Light microscopic (LM) (a-c) and SEM (d-e) images illustrating the workflow to prepare npg micropillars with tailored ligament size (f) from a bulk Au-Ag masteralloy. (a) Au-Ag ingot with nominal composition of 23 at.-% Au and 77 at.-% Ag after casting. (b) Polished surface after mechanical preparation (cutting, grinding, and polishing). (c) Surface after annealing treatment (24 h at 800 °C under Ar atmosphere) with apparent grain and twin boundaries. (d) Surface after dealloying by free corrosion (immersion for 24 h in 40 % HNO₃), revealing the npg-mesoporous structure used in the small-scale study. (e) Surface after annealing for 0.3 h at 450 °C, revealing the coarsened npg structure used in the large-scale study. The inset shows the coarsened npg structure at lower magnification. (f) Ligament size (L) distribution of the npg samples shown in d and e. The sample prepared for the small size range (red) shows an average ligament diameter $L = 28 \pm 7$ nm while the large-scale sample (green) exhibits $L = 255 \pm 80$ nm. The colored lines represent the respective Gaussian fits and illustrate the broadening of the size distribution upon coarsening with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) increasing from ~10 nm (red) to ~169 nm (green).

SI Figure 2: SEM micrographs illustrating the site-specific FIB preparation of a micropillar freestanding on top of a tip for the small-scale study. (a) On the as-dealloyed npg material a cuboid is lifted out from a selected grain. Instead of depositing a protective layer on top for preventing FIB damage during the overall preparation procedure, a large part of the sample is milled out ($\sim 10 \times 20 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$), thereby serving by itself as a protection for the sample interior from which finally the pillar is prepared. Please note that deposition could easily cause infiltration of the mesopores and therefore change the material system. (b) Transfer of the cuboid sample to a tailored tomography tip. The tip diameter at the top has been reduced by FIB milling before the transfer. (c) The cuboid is fixed by C-deposition using the gas injection system (GIS). (d) The edges of the cuboid are milled at all sides to achieve a tip-like geometry. (e) The edges are further thinned with decreased ion beam currents to improve the npg surface quality and achieve a plateau on top of the tip with a size of $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$. The respective black marked area is shown in (f). (i) Finally a micropillar is milled out from the plateau in top view using a single-pass milling scheme at a low beam current (8 pA). Please note that any direct exposure of the ion beam to the pillar prior to the final milling step was avoided to preserve the delicate porous structure. (g-i) The resulting freestanding pillar with a diameter of $\sim 400 \text{ nm}$ diameter and a length of $\sim 750 \text{ nm}$ is shown in different perspectives and within its geometry on the tip.

SI Figure 3: SEM micrographs illustrating the site-specific FIB preparation to obtain of a micropillar freestanding on top of a tip for the large-scale study. (a-b) On the coarsened npg material a cuboid ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m} \times 10 \mu\text{m} \times 15 \mu\text{m}$) is lifted out from a single grain, as identified by backscattered electron (BSE) imaging. (c) The cuboid is transferred to (d) a tomography tip with a pre-adjusted tip diameter in the range of the sample width. The cuboid is fixed on the tip by C-deposition at the outer edges. Additionally, a small amount of SEM compatible glue is applied to the tomography tip in advance of the transfer procedure. By this, a stable solid support for the latter compression experiment is granted. (e) On top of the tip a micropillar with a diameter of $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ is milled in a single milling pass. (f) Final geometry of the pillar with a tailored aspect ratio of 1 after trimming without direct exposure of the residual sample volume to the ion beam (in order to minimize FIB damage).

SI Figure 4: Crystallographic analysis of the small-scale npg pillar. (a) BFTEM image of the small-scale pillar with superimposed main crystal orientation along the pillar axis [137] and indicated regions for selected area electron diffraction (SAED) (b-e). The SAED patterns which are acquired at the outer edges of the pillar (d, e) show additional (ring pattern type) reflections, which indicate the presence of FIB-induced defects, e.g., nanocrystals¹.

SI Figure 5: Chemical analysis of the residual Ag-content in the as-dealloyed npg material by STEM-EDXS. (a) HAADF-STEM image of the ROI. (b) Respective EDXS mapping revealing the local distribution of Ag rich clusters and an overall residual Ag content of ~6 at.-%. (c) The quantification of the linescan indicated in (b) reveals a local cluster with up to 25 at.-% Ag.

SI Figure 6: Distribution of local thickness in (a) small-scale sample (Ligament size $L=30$ nm), (b) large-scale sample ($L=300$ nm), (c) experimentally informed (ExIn) and (d) geometrically constructed (GeCo) samples. Insets show the skeleton network of nanoporous structures. The color and thickness of the tubes are related to the local thickness of the ligaments. Skeletonization of (e) ExIn and (f) GeCo samples. The color of the nodes is related to the number of ligaments connected to that node. Blue, green and red nodes indicate 1, 3 and more than 3 ligaments connected to that node, respectively.

SI Figure 7: Dependency of the non-dimensional pre-factors for elastic modulus (C_E) and yield stress (C_σ) on the scaled genus density after Mangipudi et al.² with overlaid results from this work. Mangipudi et al. found a linear relationship between the scaled genus density and the pre-factors for different network topologies (spinodal structure, gyroid, np-Au) as indicated by the black dashed line ($C_\sigma = 3 \cdot \bar{g}$ and $C_E = 5 \cdot \bar{g}$). The scaled genus densities derived in this work from topological analysis on tomographic reconstructions from 360° ET and Nano-CT analysis, respectively, are indicated with vertical lines in yellow for the small-scale sample and in grey for the large-scale sample. Based on the linear relationship found by Mangipudi et al. the elastic and plastic pre-factor can be determined for both samples (horizontal dotted lines). Further on the unique combination of non-destructive tomography techniques and mechanical deformation allows the calculation of solid yield strength and solid Young's modulus based on these pre-factors. The corresponding results are summarized in table S1. The figure was adapted and reprinted from Ref.² "Topology-dependent scaling laws for the stiffness and strength of nanoporous gold", K.R. Mangipudi, E. Epler, C.A. Volkert, Acta Mater. 119, 115-122, 2016, with permission from Elsevier.

SI Figure 8: Interface shape distribution of (a) small-scale sample ($L=30$ nm), (b) large-scale sample ($L=300$ nm), (c) ExIn and (d) GeCo samples.

SI Figure 9: Comparison of (a) derived ligament yield strength and (b) ligament Young's modulus versus ligament diameter to literature data as composed by (a) Mameka et al.³ and (b) Mangipudi et al.². In the plots the standard pre-factors of the Gibson and Ashby law ($C_\sigma = 0.3$, $C_E = 1.0$) are assumed. Datapoints from this work are inserted as green crosses (small-scale sample) and red crosses (large-scale sample). In (a) literature data is comprised from small-scale testing on npg⁴⁻⁸ (grey circles) and massive Au pillars^{9,10} (grey triangles), as compiled in Ref.^{11,12}, as well as from macro-scale testing of mm-sized npg samples^{3,12} (grey stars with blue line as best fit) and various npg-polymer blends^{3,13} (yellow circles and orange squares). Please note that in case of the massive Au pillars L describes the pillar diameter. In (b) the ligament Young's modulus has been normalized to the isotropic bulk Young's modulus with $E_s^{bulk,iso} = 79 \text{ GPa}$. Here, literature data is comprised from small-scale testing on npg, namely thin-film buckling¹⁴ (blue triangles), nanoindentation^{2,7,15} (red triangles, black square, green circles), experimental⁵ (purple circle) and simulated² (red squares) pillar compression and macro-scale testing of mm-sized npg³ (yellow stars). The plot in (a) is adapted and reprinted from Ref.³ "Nanoporous Gold—Testing Macro-scale Samples to Probe Small-scale Mechanical Behavior", Mameka, N., Wang, K., Markmann, J., Lilleodden, E. T. & Weissmüller, J., *Mater. Res. Lett* **4**, 27–36, 2016 with free permission by CC BY licensing. The plot in (b) is adapted and reprinted from Ref.² "Topology-dependent scaling laws for the stiffness and strength of nanoporous gold", K.R. Mangipudi, E. Epler, C.A. Volkert, *Acta Mater.* **119**, 115-122, 2016, with permission from Elsevier.

Scaling equations and discussion about pre-factors in the Gibson and Ashby law

The macroscopic foam scaling laws derived from Gibson and Ashby¹⁶ are used to calculate the solid yield strength and the solid Young's modulus from the experimental stress-strain data for comparison with former literature studies³. For this, the relative density derived from tomography as well as the two standard pre-factors $C_E = 1.0$ and $C_\sigma = 0.3$ are used within the Gibson Ashby law. The two standard 'averaged' pre-factors have been widely used over the past decade to describe the deformation behavior of various open macroporous foams. They were also used to study the size dependency of ligament size and strength/elasticity in npg. However, their direct applicability to npg has been controversially discussed recently due to the distinct npg network structure². For comparison of data between this work and previous literature studies, the same pre-factors are applied in a pragmatic context. By doing this, the solid yield strengths of $\sigma_{y,s}^{30nm} = 791$ MPa and $\sigma_{y,s}^{300nm} = 649$ MPa and the solid Young's moduli of $E_s^{30nm} = 16$ GPa and $E_s^{300nm} = 22$ GPa are calculated. SI Figure 9 shows the results in comparison to literature data indicating the trend of smaller is stronger (compared to the yield strength of solid Au ~ 30 MPa¹⁷). Judging from an experimental point of view, it is not clear, however, whether the increase in strength between the samples of different length scales is related to the different ligament size or the slight variation in network topology/morphology. Concerning the derived Young's moduli, it is expected that the stiffness of the small-scale sample is lowered by the compliant npg network supporting the pillar below in contrast to the large-scale sample which is fabricated on top of a rigid (tungsten) support. The calculated solid Young's moduli are lower than the isotropic Young's modulus ($E_{iso} = 79$ GPa) and the Young's moduli in the respective crystal orientations ($E_{\langle 137 \rangle} = 57$ GPa and $E_{\langle 013 \rangle} = 50$ GPa) calculated theoretically from the elastic constants after Foiles¹⁸. This observation is in agreement with previous literature studies in which this finding has been discussed as an anomalous low stiffness of npg¹⁹. However, still the employment of the standard pre-factors in the Gibson and Ashby law in case of npg is heavily debated. In particular Mangipudi et al.² observed varying pre-factors for npg by comparing the stress-strain response of networks with different topologies (spinodal structure, gyroid, npg) in FE simulations. Moreover, they found a linear relationship between the elastic/plastic pre-factors and the network topology, as characterized by the scaled genus density (SI Figure 7). In the present work, we have now the unique possibility to determine both, the scaled genus density and the mechanical stress-strain response on the same sample, which is only possible by the application of non-destructive tomography techniques. By the topology dependent scaling found by Mangipudi et al.² we can now link the scaled genus density to more accurate pre-factors and such determine more accurate values for the solid yield

strength as well as the solid Young's modulus. By this, we receive elastic values which are closer to the orientation-dependent Young's moduli of Au with $E_s^{30\text{nm},\bar{g}} = 35$ GPa for the small-scale sample and $E_s^{300\text{nm},\bar{g}} = 59$ GPa for the large-scale sample. These results seem more reliable, since a strong deviation from the Young's modulus is not expected for the large-scale sample (with a ligament size of ~ 300 nm), which is mechanically loaded under controlled conditions (rigid support). Based on this also the derived values for the solid yield strength should be more realistic, which suggests an even stronger size effect in plasticity with $\sigma_y^{30\text{nm},\bar{g}} = 1041$ MPa for the small-scale sample and $\sigma_y^{300\text{nm},\bar{g}} = 878$ MPa for the large-scale sample.

SI Figure 10: (a) Digital image correlation analysis (DIC) which is applied to *in situ* SEM image series taken during npg micropillar compression reveals the strong evolution of local strain gradients during deformation and, in particular (c) local yielding in the early stages of deformation before macroscopic yielding (here shown after unloading at low strain values). The local strain is analyzed along the direction of the pillar axis from top to bottom. The applied macroscopic strain ϵ is indicated in the upper right corner. In (b) a representative stress-strain plot is shown indicating the three stages of deformation: 1. Initial 'elastic'-like loading with yielding of just weak spots. 2. Macroscopical yielding when the average strength of the npg network is reached, followed by subsequent hardening. 3. Densification at high strain as soon as pore space is minimized and ligaments are touching each other.

SI Figure 11: (a) Crucial effects of local strain localization on the deformation behavior of a micropillar causing failure by buckling. (b) Origin of local strain localization by intrinsic network inhomogeneities and weak spots. Here shown: Strain concentration in a micropillar containing a flaw in its lower section. The strain is analyzed along the direction of the pillar axis from top to bottom by DIC techniques. The applied macroscopic strain ε is indicated in the upper right corner.

SI Figure 12: Resolved shear stresses along the Burgers vectors of 12 possible partial dislocations in a representative junction of GeCo sample ($L=30$ nm) before the initiation of plasticity in this junction (at 1.8% strain). Displayed here are solely two atomic layers on specific slip planes, with the surface mesh appearing semi-transparent.

SI Figure 13: (a) True stress and (b) normalized dislocation density (normalized by mean ligament size) as function of strain of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of GeCo samples with different ligament sizes. (c) Atomic stress (resolved along $A\beta$ direction on slip plane (b)) states in a representative junction of GeCo samples with different ligament sizes ($L=5, 7.5, 10$ and 30 nm) before compression.

SI Figure 14: Dislocation analysis of (a) scaled-down ($L=5$ nm) and (b) real-size ($L=30$ nm) ExIn samples. (c) Zoomed-in areas marked in (b) where stacking fault tetrahedra (SFT) and dislocation walls are widely distributed.

SI Figure 15: TEM analysis (ZA $\langle 110 \rangle$) on a FIB lamella extracted from a compressed npg particle confirming the presence of small-angle grain boundaries (SAGBs) induced by very localized deformation of the particle due to the small cross-sectional area in its upper part close to the indenter contact. (a) Overview image in bright field TEM (BFTEM) mode showing the cross-section of the particle with close-up of upper region in (b). (c) Close-up from yellow area marked in (b) in high resolution TEM (HRTEM) mode. (d) Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) from image (c) as well as from the three indicated ROIs (2, 3, 4) in image (c). The relative in-plane lattice rotation is measured from the FFTs and detected to be about 11° between ROI 1 and 3 confirming the presence of a SAGB. The studied npg particles presented here are synthesized according to the procedure of Wang et al.²⁰

by solid-state dewetting of Au-Ag thin films and subsequent dealloying. Compression is performed *in situ* in the SEM with a flat punch. The relative layer thickness is chosen to yield a nominal relative density of ~30-40 % in the as-dealloyed state. The mean ligament diameter is in this case ~20 nm.

SI Figure 16: Defect analysis on a TEM lamella prepared from the small-scale pillar after deformation in $\langle 110 \rangle$ ZA as visible by SAED and FFT analysis. The analysis reveals present (b) SAGBs, (c) micro-twins (MTs) and (d) stacking faults (SFs). (a) Overview image (BFTEM) of the pillar cross section with respective ROIs (b, c, d) studied by

HRTEM as well as indicated area used for the correlative atomistic simulations (MD). The local geometrical configuration of the respective ROIs is shown enlarged in the insets (upper left) showing (b) a single bended ligament, (c) a very small ligament with a size of ~2 nm and (d) a ligament junction. The overlaid lines in (b) and the enlarged images in (c) and (d) indicate the stacking order of the {111} planes and visualize in (b) the change in lattice rotation and in (c) and (d) the change of the stacking sequence due to the defects. In (b) the inserted half plane of one single dislocation within the SAGB is highlighted in the inverse FFT (IFFT).

SI Figure 17: Evolution of defects and orientational disorder in npg with increasing local strain level described qualitatively from (a) undeformed to (b) low, (c) medium and (d) high local strain concentration. The images are acquired on a FIB lamella extracted from a deformed npg micropillar at different ROIs which show a different amount of local strain level (as depicted in SI Figure 10/11). In the undeformed state (a) mainly just a few MTs are present, which lead to additional $[111]$ and $\{200\}$ type reflections in the corresponding FFT (green circles), while the variety and density of defects and disorder increases with increasing strain.

SI Figure 18: Illustration of strain localization around an intrinsic flaw in the npg network structure of a FIB prepared micropillar after compression. The figure shows a volume rendering (side view) of the micropillar studied by nano X-ray computed tomography (nano-CT) (a) before and (b) after about 50% compression. In each state the exterior (left) and a slice through the central part (right) is shown. The flaw (arrow) can appear as an intrinsic defect after the dealloying procedure.

SI Figure 19: Mechanism of formation of deformation-induced stacking fault tetrahedron (SFT) in ExIn sample ($L=30$ nm) during the simulated compression test. Only atoms in stacking faults are shown here in half-transparent. The direction of the dislocation line is indicated by red arrows, while the Burgers vector is denoted using Greek/Roman letters in the Thompson tetrahedron representation. The mesh illustrates the free surface. (a) Two leading partial dislocations δC (d) and αC (a) nucleated simultaneously from the free surface and followed by the corresponding trailing partial dislocations $A\delta$ (d) and $D\alpha$ (a). (b) The full dislocations AC (d) (δC (d) + $A\delta$ (d)) and DC (a) (αC (a) + $D\alpha$ (a)) moved towards the center of strut and interacted with each other. A stair rod dislocation $\delta\alpha$ was formed from the interaction of the two leading partial dislocations δC (d) and αC (a). The full dislocation DC (a) cross-slipped to (b) plane at the free surfaces. (c) Then, the full dislocation DC (b) (βC (b) + $D\beta$ (b)) slipped on (b) plane and jointed with the full dislocation DC (a) (αC (a) + $D\alpha$ (a)) by a stair rod dislocation $\alpha\beta$. (d) The partial dislocation βC (b) interacted with δC (d) by forming a stair rod dislocation $\delta\beta$. A partial dislocation γD (c) nucleated and slipped on (c) plane and then interacted with $D\beta$ (b) by forming a stair rod dislocation $\gamma\beta$. (e-f) Afterwards, the partial dislocation γD (c) interacted with $D\alpha$ (a) and $\delta\alpha$ by forming a partial dislocation $B\delta$ (d) on (d) plane and a partial dislocation γB (c) on (c) plane (γD (c) + $D\alpha$ (a) \rightarrow $B\delta$ (d) + γB (c) + $\delta\alpha$). (g) Then the partial dislocations γB (c) and $B\delta$ (d) moved towards the free surfaces, a stair-rod dislocation $\gamma\delta$ was left behind. (h) After these dislocation nucleation and interactions, a SFT consists of six stair-rod dislocations formed near the free surfaces.

SI Figure 20: Mechanism of formation of deformation-induced small-angle grain boundary (SAGB) in ExIn sample ($L=30$ nm) during the simulated compression test. Only atoms in stacking faults are show here in half-transparent. The direction of the dislocation line is indicated by red arrows, while the Burgers vector is denoted using Greek/Roman letters in the Thompson tetrahedron representation. The mesh illustrates the free surface. (a) At 4.46% strain, the first dislocations emitted from the free surface and propagated along slip planes (b). (b-d) The full dislocations AD (b) ($A\beta + \beta D$) kept nucleating from the same and adjacent nucleation sites, and dislocation arrays were observed inside of the ligament. (e) At 5.89% strain, a partial dislocation $C\beta$ nucleated from the free surface and glided perpendicular to the dislocation array. (f-g) After interaction with full dislocations AD (b), dislocation nodes with branches extended to form intrinsic stacking faults were observed. (h-i) The partial dislocations $C\beta$ and full dislocations AD (b) continuously nucleated from the same nucleation sites and interacted with each other by forming triangular stacking faults bounded by three different partial dislocations ($A\beta$, $C\beta$ and βD) on slip plane (b). The SAGBs consisted of these triangular stacking fault patterns which are widely existed in the real-size ExIn and GeCo NPG samples, but not in the scaled-down samples.

SI Figure 21: Resolved shear stresses along the Burgers vectors of 12 possible partial dislocations in a representative junction of ExIn sample ($L=30$ nm) where a SFT will form in further deformation before the initiation of plasticity in this junction (at 12.6% strain). Displayed here are solely two atomic layers on specific slip planes, with the surface mesh appearing semi-transparent.

SI Figure 22: (a) Normalized resolved shear stresses ($\sigma_{RSS} = \frac{\sum_i \sigma_{RSS}^i V^i}{\sum_i V^i}$, normalized by true stress $\sigma_{ZZ} = \frac{\sum_i \sigma_{ZZ}^i V^i}{\sum_i V^i}$, where V^i is the atomic volume of atom i) of the simulated npg samples ($L=30$ nm) in elastic deformation regime ($\sigma_{ZZ} \approx 110$ MPa) and the corresponding Schmid factors of leading partial dislocations. (b) Standard deviations of the resolved shear stresses of the simulated npg, nanowire (NW) and bulk oriented in [137]-direction at 300 K in elastic deformation regime ($\sigma_{ZZ} \approx 110$ MPa).

Table S 1: Summary of mechanical properties of small- and large-scale npg samples under *in situ* compression tests. The Young's moduli were fitted in a range of 0.01 strain ($L=300$ nm) and 0.02 strain ($L=30$ nm) in elastic regime. The effective Young's moduli (E^{unload}) of the sponges were calculated from the 1st unloading ($L=30$ nm) and from the 2nd unloading ($L=300$ nm) due to a very small displacement before the 2nd unloading. The solid yield strengths were calculated with the standard pre-factors of $C_\sigma = 0.3$ and $C_E = 1$ and the two relative densities derived from tomography and analytics. The scaled genus density \bar{g} and the topology-dependent pre-factors were calculated as $C_\sigma^{\bar{g}}=3 \cdot \bar{g}$ and $C_E^{\bar{g}}=5 \cdot \bar{g}$ after Mangipudi et al.².

Sample		$L=30$ nm	$L=300$ nm
Global yield point (engineering)	σ_y (MPa)	50	48
	ε_y	0.048	0.048
Young's modulus (GPa)	E^{unload}	1.7 (1 st , $\varepsilon=0.03$) 1.7 (2 nd , $\varepsilon=0.04$) 2.1 (8 th , $\varepsilon=0.12$) 2.2 (11 th , $\varepsilon=0.16$)	2.7 (1 st , $\varepsilon=0.01$) 3.4 (2 nd , $\varepsilon=0.02$) 6.0 (7 th , $\varepsilon=0.12$)
	E^{load}	1.2	1.5
Relative density	φ^{tomo}	0.354	0.393
	φ^{analy}	0.320	0.378
Solid yield strength (MPa)	$\sigma_{y,s}^{\text{tomo}}$	791	649
	$\sigma_{y,s}^{\text{analy}}$	920	688
Solid Young's modulus (GPa)	E_s^{tomo}	16	22
	E_s^{analy}	13	24
Scaled genus density \bar{g}		0.076	0.074
Pre-factors after \bar{g}	$C_\sigma^{\bar{g}}$	0.23	0.22
	$C_E^{\bar{g}}$	0.38	0.37
Solid yield strength from $C_\sigma^{\bar{g}}$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{y,s}^{\text{tomo},\bar{g}}$	1041	878
	$\sigma_{y,s}^{\text{analy},\bar{g}}$	1210	929
Solid Young's modulus from $C_E^{\bar{g}}$ (GPa)	$E_s^{\text{tomo},\bar{g}}$	35	59
	$E_s^{\text{analy},\bar{g}}$	42	64

Table S 2: Summary of mechanical properties of simulated npg samples with different ligament sizes under compression tests. The Young's moduli were fitted in a range of 0.02 strain in elastic regime.

Sample	Global yield point (engineering)		Global yield point (True)		Onset of plasticity (True)		Young's modulus (GPa)		
	$\sigma_{y,eng}$ (MPa)	$\epsilon_{y,eng}$	$\sigma_{y,zz}$ (MPa)	$\epsilon_{y,zz}$	$\sigma_{y,zz}^*$ (MPa)	$\epsilon_{y,zz}^*$	E_{eng}^{unload}	E_{eng}^{load}	E_{zz}^{load}
ExIn $L=30$ nm	72	0.027	190	0.026	133	0.013	9.2 ($\epsilon=0.16$)	7.6	10.8
ExIn $L=10$ nm	62	0.032	174	0.033	111	0.020	-	3.2	5.8
ExIn $L=7.5$ nm	57	0.044	165	0.045	102	0.029	-	2.3	5.4
ExIn $L=5$ nm	44	0.044	149	0.056	85	0.023	-	1.7	2.8
GeCo $L=30$ nm	153	0.024	423	0.024	401	0.021	-	14.0	19.9
GeCo $L=10$ nm	143	0.037	394	0.039	340	0.032	-	5.3	12.9
GeCo $L=7.5$ nm	143	0.046	404	0.048	315	0.035	-	4.6	11.6
GeCo $L=5$ nm	132	0.052	369	0.051	275	0.038	-	3.6	10.0
FE $L=300$ nm	41	0.051	-	-	-	-	2.5 (1 st , $\epsilon=0.01$) 3.3 (2 nd , $\epsilon=0.02$) 5.4 (7 th , $\epsilon=0.12$)	0.8	-

Table S 3: List of Schmid factors of slip systems under uniaxial loading in [137]-oriented FCC metals.

Slip system	Schmid factor
$B\alpha$ (a)	0.320
$C\alpha$ (a)	0.040
$D\alpha$ (a)	0.280
BC (a)	0.208
BD (a)	0.346
CD (a)	0.138
$A\beta$ (b)	0.431
$C\beta$ (b)	0
$D\beta$ (b)	0.431
AC (b)	0.249
AD (b)	0.498
CD (b)	0.249
$A\gamma$ (c)	0.072
$B\gamma$ (c)	0.144
$D\gamma$ (c)	0.216
AB (c)	0.042
AD (c)	0.166
BD (c)	0.208
$A\delta$ (d)	0.088
$B\delta$ (d)	0.352
$C\delta$ (d)	0.439
AB (d)	0.152
AC (d)	0.304
BC (d)	0.457

References

1. Petegem, S. Van *et al.* On the Microstructure of Nanoporous Gold: An X-ray Diffraction Study. *Nano Lett.* **9**, 1158–1163 (2009).
2. Mangipudi, K. R., Epler, E. & Volkert, C. A. Topology-dependent scaling laws for the stiffness and strength of nanoporous gold. *Acta Mater.* **119**, 115–122 (2016).
3. Mameka, N., Wang, K., Markmann, J., Lilleodden, E. T. & Weissmüller, J. Nanoporous Gold—Testing Macro-scale Samples to Probe Small-scale Mechanical Behavior. *Mater. Res. Lett.* **4**, 27–36 (2016).
4. Biener, J. *et al.* Size Effects on the Mechanical Behavior of Nanoporous Au. *Nano Lett.* **6**, 2379–2382 (2006).
5. Volkert, C. A., Lilleodden, E. T., Kramer, D. & Weissmüller, J. Approaching the theoretical strength in nanoporous Au. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **89**, 61920 (2006).
6. Hodge, A. M. *et al.* Scaling equation for yield strength of nanoporous open-cell foams. *Acta Mater.* **55**, 1343–1349 (2006).
7. Biener, J., Hodge, A. M., Hamza, A. V, Hsiung, L. M. & Jr., J. H. S. Nanoporous Au: A high yield strength material. *J. Appl. Phys.* **97**, 24301 (2005).
8. Lee, D. *et al.* Microfabrication and mechanical properties of nanoporous gold at the nanoscale. *Scr. Mater.* **56**, 437–440 (2007).
9. Greer, J. R., Oliver, W. C. & Nix, W. D. Size dependence of mechanical properties of gold at the micron scale in the absence of strain gradients. *Acta Mater.* **53**, 1821–1830 (2005).
10. Volkert, C. A. & Lilleodden, E. T. Size effects in the deformation of sub-micron Au columns. *Philos. Mag.* **86**, 5567–5579 (2006).
11. Biener, J., Hamza, A. V & Hodge, A. M. Deformation Behavior of Nanoporous Metals. in *Micro and Nano Mechanical Testing of Materials and Devices* (eds. Yang, F. & Li, J. C. M.) 118–135 (Springer US, 2008). doi:10.1007/978-0-387-78701-5_6
12. Jin, H.-J. *et al.* Deforming nanoporous metal: Role of lattice coherency. *Acta Mater.* **57**, 2665–2672 (2009).
13. Wang, K. *et al.* Nanoporous-gold-based composites: toward tensile ductility. *NPG Asia Mater.* **7**, e187 (2015).
14. Mathur, A. & Erlebacher, J. Size dependence of effective Young's modulus of nanoporous gold. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **90**, 2005–2008 (2007).
15. Hodge, A. M. *et al.* Ag effects on the elastic modulus values of nanoporous Au foams. *J. Mater. Res.* **24**, 1600–1606 (2009).
16. Gibson, L. J. & Ashby, M. F. *Cellular solids: structure and properties*. (Cambridge university press, 1999).

17. Savitskii, E. & Prince, A. *Handbook of precious metals*. (Hemi- sphere Publishing Company, 1969).
18. Park, H. S. & Zimmerman, J. A. Modeling inelasticity and failure in gold nanowires. *Phys. Rev. B* **72**, 54106 (2005).
19. Ngô, B. N. D. *et al.* Anomalous compliance and early yielding of nanoporous gold. *Acta Mater.* **93**, 144–155 (2015).
20. Wang, D. & Schaaf, P. Nanoporous gold nanoparticles. *J. Mater. Chem.* **22**, 5344–5348 (2012).